

IMPROVEMENT OF PENETRATION RESISTANCE OF AMINE CURED EPOXY RESIN FOR CONCRETE LINING BY ION EXCHANGE ZEOLITE UNDER SULFURIC ACID

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Introduction

Concrete is widely used as a structural material in many applications around the world. However, concrete vessels and pipes particularly those used in wastewater treatment systems are indirectly affected by generation of hydrogen sulfide gas from the reduction of sulfates in the fluids by sulfate reducing bacteria [1]. This arises because in subsequent oxidizing environments, for example in the presence of sulfur oxidizing bacteria, H₂S is re-converted to sulfuric acid at low pH, which can cause severe damage to concrete and mortar [2].

Epoxy-based coatings and linings have excellent chemical and corrosion resistance, high mechanical strength, good adhesion to a variety of substrates and a combination of other properties, which make them a particular material of choice [3]. These epoxy resin are used with various fillers. However, the influence of various filler additives towards the propagation of sulfate in epoxy resin and how this might influence the corrosion damage mechanism of sulfuric acid to concrete is still not clear.

In this research considers the influence of two ion-exchange zeolite materials, and nominally inert fillers (i.e. alumina), on the transport properties (diffusion, permeation, etc.) and reactivity of sulfuric acid in amine-cured epoxy resin.

Road depression accident associated with Sewerage facilities
Exhibit : Tokyo Metropolitan Government Bureau of Sewerage

Mechanism of microbial corrosion

Experimental methods

Materials and Specimens

Matrix Resin

Amine cured Epoxy Resin (E206s:Konishi Co., Ltd.)
 Base resin : Bisphenol A Epoxy
 Hardener : Diamine Curing Agent

Filler

Cation Exchange Zeolite
 Basic type (Na⁺ cation) (Zeorum 320NAA, Tosoh Corp.)
 =>ZNa
 Acidic type (H⁺ cation) (Zeorum 320HOA, Tosoh Corp.)
 =>ZHS
 General Filler
 Alumina (Al/Nippon Light Metal Co., Ltd.) =>Al

Table Types and properties of fillers.

	320NAA	320HOA	Alumina
Mean diameter [μm]	6	6	4
Bulk density [g/cm ³]	0.37	0.32	0.99
Pore size [Å]	9	9	-
Cation [-]	Na ⁺	H ⁺	-

Immersion test

Specimens were immersed in 10 mass % sulfuric acid at 50° C. Initial weights and dimensions of specimens were measured before immersion.

Analytical method

The degradation analysis of these materials included measure of weight, visual observation, scanning electron microscope (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS), a bending test.

The penetration depth of sulfur was calculated by:

$$X = (t_0 - t) / 2 \quad (1)$$
 Where, X is penetration depth, t₀ is the total thickness of specimen before immersion, and t is that of the nominally non-penetrated part after immersion..

Immersion test

S element EDS mapping of cross section of specimens immersed in 10 mass% H₂SO₄ solutions after 24 hours.

Result and discussion

Properties of Specimens

	EP	ZHS	ZNa	Al
Flexural strength [MPa]	79.2	77.8	80.5	79.2
Flexural modulus [GPa]	2.38	3.16	3.31	3.83
Density [g/cm ³]	1.14	1.28	1.31	1.50

Penetration rate of S element

	EP	ZHS	ZNa	Al
λ [mm/h ^{0.5}]	9.57.E-2	5.34.E-2	7.73.E-2	1.23.E-1

=>The penetration velocity of ZHS was about 55% later than Neat resin

Conclusion

The results confirm that addition of ion exchange materials to epoxy-amine resins can both improve the resistance of the material to sulfuric acid and reduce its diffusion rate. This demonstrates a potentially promising method for the control of biogenic sulfuric acid corrosion of concrete sewer pipes although care does need to be taken over the choice of filler material in order to optimize the performance of the lining system.

Reference

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Comparison of "S" element penetration depth of all materials